

TRADITIONS OF FOLLOWING NAVOY IN USMAN AZIM'S POETRY

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Annotation: *In the article, examples of creativity created as a continuation of classical poetry traditions, following his predecessors-teachers, who are a part of the poet Usman Azim's poetry, are studied. In this case, its tatabbu and mukhammas are taken as the object of the image. An analysis of his creative approach to aruz weight is given. Also, the role of the artistic language of the poet's creativity in bringing out the pathos of his poems in the traditional way is discussed. The features of form and content of poems are revealed.*

Key words: *traditions of poetry, tatabbu, tazmin, mukhammas, aruz, poetic forms and genres, traditionalism and innovation.*

When talking about contemporary Uzbek poetry, we can say that Usman Azim's work occupies special golden pages. Especially in recent years, the poet's creativity is one of the topics that is being researched a lot. The following article is also one of the wonderful studies that shed light on the creative aspects of the poet, in which opinions are presented about the variety of genres and forms of the poet's poetry.

First of all, a few words about the poet's poetic style. Uzbek poetry saw many poets during its historical development. Their styles, scope of genres, range of topics are different. That's why they got individuality. For example, the light folk style of Erkin Vahidov, the poetry of Abdulla Oripov with thoughtful nationalistic ideas, or the poetry of Khurshid Davron with pride in history are their most characteristic features. In one word, they are the definitions when it is necessary. When it comes to Usman Azim's poetry, if it were up to us, we would say that the poet's poetry is royal.

Because no matter what topic he writes, he has pathos and says the last word with burning sentences. There are hardly any doubts in his thoughts. Even when he writes about situations that create a depressed mood, such as grief and separation, there are tones of solemnity and dervish approval of fate. Poet's poems often appear in the highest veils of feelings. When Usman Azim's poetry is studied from the point of view of diversity of genres and forms, it is possible to divide them into poems written in the genres and forms that were created

based on the traditions of Uzbek poetry and are used in world literature.

When viewed from this point of view, the poet's poetry is ghazal, masnavi, dirge, landscape, letter, hasbi hol, tatabbu; If we study stanza poems such as three, four, and five stanzas on the basis of traditionalism, many ballads, elegy, invective, white verse, free verse, etc. found in the poet's work are works created under the influence of world literature. should be studied as examples.

Usman Azim's creative nature is more innovative than traditional. When the poet's poetry is viewed from the point of view of the content and the scope of the subject, it can be felt that he is a modern poet first of all. The fact that the classical genres found in his poetry undergo some formal changes and are presented in a different way in the poet's work explains our above opinion to a certain extent. Tatabbu to "Khamsa", "Mercy to the memory of Kazakh poet Kenashlik Mirzabekov" ("Saylanma, p. 244), as well as several ghazals and masnavis written in finger weight, which are included in various collections of the poet, are examples of this.

In the Dictionary of Literary Studies, nazira and tatabbu are defined as follows: "NAZIRA (ar. - similar, similar thing, example) - a poem created by following another poet's poem, in the form of an analogy or as a response to it. In Eastern literature, N. bitish is a very common tradition, which takes the form of a creative competition with contemporary poets or predecessors. In N., the poet takes exactly one stanza or verse from another poet's poem and continues it or adds it to his own poem imbibes the stanza or verse exactly quoted.

In Persian-Tajik literature, such poems are referred to as tatabbu (Ar. following something, to follow), but in Uzbek poetry, the term N. is more popular. Sometimes the term compensation is also used in relation to N. However, in some sources related to science and art, there is a serious difference between tazmin and N.: quoting another poet's verse or verse exactly in a poem is tazmin, as a response to someone else's poem, and a poem written in the style of a literary competition is referred to as N. or tatabbu. (page 200)

At first glance, Osman Azim's poem "Tatabbu to Hamsa" seems like a poetic title, it has nothing to do with tatabbu. But if you look deeper into the content of the poem and compare it with the quote given above, there will be no doubt that it is a tatabbu. Because following the predecessors of the first rules of this genre, the poet wrote 5 poems

belonging to this poetic series: "Haytrat ul-Abror", "Farhad and Shirin", "Layli and Majnun", "Sabayi Sayor", "Wall or Saddi Iskandari". " is called. In terms of content, he puts a philosophical thought in the first poem of the series, following the traditions of poetry. The poem is relatively short,

*I have seen a lot of wisdom in this world
Wouldn't it be funny if I tell you a secret?
When I walk towards the sun, my shadow is behind me,
My shadow is ahead if I run away from the sun.*

The name and the philosophical content alone do not deny that some rules of tatabbu have been fulfilled in this poem. The poet follows Navoi in this regard. In literature, the use of the image of a shadow as an unfaithful friend is also found in other poets. For example, Uzbek poet Asqad Mukhtar in his poem "Bir Top Orik" says that he made a friend with the shadow of an apricot tree on a sunny day, but could not find this friend near him on a cloudy day. Also, in the Kazakh poet Abay's work "Naqliya sozlar" "A bad friend is like a shadow. "If the day dawns on your forehead, you will not be able to escape, if a cloud gathers over your head, you will not be able to find it." There is also a shadow in Usman Azim's poem above from such images. Only here, when you strive for the top, there will be many people who will follow you, otherwise, they will leave you easily. The fact that the life wisdom about the possibility is given with strong irony shows the style of the poet. The fact that the poems included in the category are not in the form of an epic shows that the tatabbu is based on the content rather than the form. In fact, in the science of literature, tatabbu is studied among the genres named according to the content. In the 2nd volume of the book "Literary Types and Genres" "1. In terms of content. Genres based on aesthetic pathos and specific content direction" is defined as tatabbu as follows:" But nazira is not copying or imitation; the theme, content, and form are treated creatively, the spirit of the era and personal style are instilled in all of these literary events; change occurs not only in the idea, but also in the artistic form" (p. 173).

"Farhad and Shirin" is the second of the poem "Tatabbu to Hamsa"; third, the poems "Layli and Majnun" are about love, just like "Khamsa" epics. We can say that the name and theme indicate that these poems are tatabbu. The fact that this poem was created as a dialogue "Farhod and Shirin" also reminds us of Navoi epic (we remember the dialogue between Khusrav and Farhod in the epic). In

this poem, words such as bad, ghulam, zamon, tozon, hazan are taken from the language of the lover and the lover. , finally the nature of the sacrificer (hazan) is described. The fact that the poetic sentences are fully covered in short lines (with 4 syllables) and the words whose main content is rhyme gives the impression that the immutable rules of the eternal nature of love are presented like petroglyphs. The fact that the heroes of the poem are Farhad and Shirin is a preservation of traditionalism in tatabbu. The next poem in the series is called "Layli and Majnun". The characters are Laili and Majnun. In fact, these images are mentioned a lot in poetry and are even used as synonyms for the word love. This is exactly how it is used in this poem.

- *We are poor in the desert of Hijran.*

-*Layli-yu This is madness.*

- *We are hard-pressed for Visol.*

-*layli-yu This is madness ...!*

Even if we replace the words ``Layli-yu Majnunlik" with words of love, the meaning will come out, but the poetic poetics will disappear. We know that in Hamsanavis, the third epic should be on the theme of love and should be devoted to the love of Laila and Majnun. It can be said that the poet followed the traditions of tatabbu in his style.

The fourth poem of the series is called "Sabayi Sayor". In this, the poet refers to the image of the tourist, aliens in "Sabayi Sayyor" and tells his philosophical thoughts about life and the world through their speech. That is, the world "There is no lamentation except for the song", "The original beauty is hidden from the eye", "The step is the pleasure of the soul", "The friendship of a friend to a friend". "He flowed like sand in my palm", "He disappeared in the image of an angel", "There is a man in an old building" Then seven thoughts are summarized and a conclusion is given, the Invisible shouts: "Look carefully... The world consists of life and death" . How unique the poem is from the point of view of poetic discovery. First of all, if the philosophy in the poem is zalvory; secondly, the fact that the philosophical thoughts in it are quoted from the language of aliens is a unique expression of the traditional thoughts of Eastern mystical poetry about the transience of the world and the fact that everyone is a guest in this world. However, Usman Azim does not advocate obedience to the fate and faithful worship like Sufi poets, he calls humanity to struggle, saying "The world

¹ Usmon Azim. Saylanma."Sharq" nashriyot-matbaa konsernining bosh tahririyati. Toshkent- 1995-yil, 432-bet.

consists of life and death". The last poem included in "Khamsa-ga tatabbu" is given under the title "Wall or Saddi Iskandari", and only by its title we can say that it follows its predecessors. This poem does not remind us of "Saddi Iskandari" either in its content or in its form. There are sad tones in it that death is right and that everyone leaves the world in the end. The reader who is familiar with the content of "Saddi Iskandari" certainly remembers the story of the hero of the work, Iskandar, who took his hands out of the coffin. This poem also refers to the most impressive scenes in the epic.

In the poetry of Osman Azim, there are also poems that fully express the traditions of classical poetry in form and content. The poet's poem "Mukhammas to Navoi's ghazal" can be an example of our opinion.

The poem has a traditional rhyming, like all mukhammas written following another poet's ghazal: aaaaa bbbba, cccaa..., it is written in the common ramali musmuli mahzuf weight of Aruz:

- I don't know what my name is, my king in the sky

- V - - / - V - - / - V - - - / - V -

- I didn't know if it was love or love

- V - - / - V - - / - V - - - / - V -

- I didn't notice the pain of your soul, I didn't know your death

- V - - / - V - - / - V - - - / - V -

- I don't know why Tarki made love

- V - - / - V - - / - V - - - / - V -

- This is my anger, I did not know my sin.

- V - - / - V - - / - V - - - / - V -

It is an artistically perfect poem written on the theme of romantic love with seven stanzas of traditional rhyming. Analyzing the poem, we can "recognize" the creator of the poem, Usman Azim, from the ever-increasing hijran tones, the mental portals of the crazy lyrical hero. In the poem, "One hope, I will not die in unbelief and sorrow", "I wish I could understand, who is the prince among slaves", "My name does not come, I am poor, but look at me, Oh, look at my lunatic rope at the height of my pain" is one of those verses.

The classical traditions of Usman Azim's poetry can be seen in the genres of ghazal, masnavi, letter, and dirge. Only in the work of the poet, most of these poems do not fully express the rules of genre and form, they gain their uniqueness. This is a topic to be researched separately.

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